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Case studies from large European (Horizon 2020) projects to refine testing strategies

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In the context of several projects (e.g. EU-ToxRisk and Riskhunt3R) overarching strategies for NAM-based risk assessment have been developed. They are being integrated into the Alternative Safety Profiling Algorithm (ASPA), which is an IATA with a very broad scope, and a defined structure. The latter means that not only building blocks have been defined, but that defined connections between these blocks are being established and further refined. The ultimate goal is to generate a structure that resembles a defined approach (DA). Various case studies have been set up to probe the functionality of the ASPA and to use the learning from the studies to further improve the ASPA. Two exemplary studies deal with the DNT hazard assessment of agrochemicals. Exemplary compounds are picoxystrobin (from the group of strobilurin fungicides) and thiacloprid (from the group of neonicotinoid insecticides). A number of steps along the ASPA will be demonstrated, using picoxystrobin as example. Strobilurins serve as example for challenges posed by the uneven distribution of toxicants in a test system and for the types of approaches required to quantify key event relationships in an AOP.

Summary

The development and initial use of the developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) in vitro test battery (DNT-IVB) has been a milestone in the transition from traditional animal-based testing for DNT towards next generation risk assessment (NGRA) approaches. As all new approach methodologies (NAM) of the DNT-IVB have a high readiness level, the data output is considered to be robust. However, the transition from test data to toxicological knowledge and further to the use in risk assessment needs to be defined. Here, a two-step process is presented. In a first step, the activity calls generated during a screen need to be followed up to define potential toxicants (confirmation testing). In a next step, information from all DNT-IVB NAM needs to be integrated and combined with other information sources. In the course of such an integrated approach to testing and assessment (IATA) process, also toxicokinetics need to be considered for risk assessment. An algorithmically structured, multi-tier approach to such an IATA was presented. This alternative safety-profiling algorithm (ASPA) has been established and is being refined by EU-funded projects of the ASPIS cluster, with a leading role being taken by Riskhut3R. It was outlined in the presentation and then exemplified, using the strobilurin fungicide picoxystrobin as example. Based on toxicity to neural crest cell function (UKN2 assay for migration), on a mechanistic rationale (mitochondrial respiratory chain inhibition) and on a careful toxicokinetics extrapolation, it was suggested that there is an at least 80-fold offset between the highest expected internal exposure and the lowest concentrations triggering adversity. Such data may be used in a final ASPA module for risk assessment.

Introduction

Developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) is one of the more complex domains of toxicology, compared with e.g. the assessment of acute topical toxicity to skin and eyes. The animal-based guideline studies, e.g. according to OECD TG426, are amongst the most complex and resource requiring of all test methods in toxicology. The reason for this is that developmental neurotoxicants may act through many targets, affect multiple pathways and cell types and lead to a large panel of adverse outcomes on the level of nervous system structural organisation or function (Smirnova et al., 2014, 2024; Celardo et al., 2025). It has, therefore been considered extremely difficult to assess chemicals for DNT hazards, based on non-animal novel approach methodologies (NAM).

DNT is often assessed in humans by complex neuro-functional and cognition tests. To allow the testing by NAMs, the concepts of toxicity endophenotypes (TEP) and key neurodevelopmental processes (KNDP) have been important (Bal-Price et al., 2015, 2018; Kadereit et al., 2012). Briefly, it is assumed that all apical endpoints assessed during DNT testing are due to structural or functional disturbances of neural connectivity (TEP) and that this may be caused by the disturbance of one or more KNDPs (e.g. migration, neurite growth, differentiation, myelination, synapse formation or neural network formation). The latter processes and their disturbance by chemicals can all be modelled and assessed by NAMs (Celardo et al., 2025).

Based on this, it has been hypothesised that a battery of NAMs, assessing KNDPs, can be assembled (Bal-Price et al., 2015, 2018). With a sufficiently broad coverage of KNDPs, such a battery may identify a potential DNT hazard of test chemicals (Smirnova et al., 2014, 2024). Indeed, initial versions of a DNT in vitro battery (DNT-IVB) have been assembled and tested with reference chemicals (Aschner et al., 2017) and a large number of additional compounds to explore the response dynamics (Blum et al., 2023; Carstens et al., 2022). The accuracy is > 80%. To increase confidence in the results generated by NAMs of the DNT-IVB, readiness criteria have been developed and evaluated. Important questions for the future are how the battery hits are further processed, how test positives relate to AOPs (Leist et al., 2017; Hartung et al., 2024) and how this knowledge is integrated and interpreted in the context of integrated approaches to testing and assessment (IATA) (Blum et al., 2023; Cöllen et al., 2025).

Connecting NAM-based screening and risk assessment

The very first NAMs that were validated and formed the basis of OECD test guidelines (e.g. for phototoxicity or eye irritation) were assumed to make predictions on apical toxicity outcomes that may be used for risk assessment or classification of chemicals according to GHS. Since then, it has become clear, that individual NAMs can hardly provide such information, especially in the more complex toxicological domains (developmental and reproductive toxicity, systemic target organ toxicity, carcinogenicity) (Leist et al., 2014). A more refined concept for the interpretation of NAM data has been developed (Fig. 1). According to this concept, it can be assumed that many NAMs are a tool to sort test chemicals into hits and non-hits (according to the data interpretation procedure (DIP) of the NAM). Each of the DNT-IVB NAM has such a DIP, as defined in the respective ToxTemp forms (Cöllen et al., 2024; Krebs et al., 2019, Blum et al., 2025). For assays, used in a screening mode, several follow-up steps are necessary (e.g. confirmation testing in various assay setups, control for potential technical artefacts, etc.) to show that a hit (activity call) should be considered a candidate toxicant (Smirnova et al., 2024). The follow-up and confirmation of hits should be considered a general principle of toxicology, be it traditional or next-generation risk assessment (NGRA)-based (Leist et al., 2024; Magel et al., 2024).

At this stage, data on the test chemical would, in most cases, be integrated with other types of information (information on toxicokinetics and external exposure as well as data from other assays) for a risk assessment or classification of the chemical. This process of collecting, integrating and interpreting data from different information domains takes place within an IATA process (Fig. 1). To some degree, these considerations also apply to non-hits. Altogether, this means that hits from the DNT-IVB need to be fed

into a processing procedure in order to come to regulatory conclusions. A special form of structured IATA, i.e. the Alternative Safety Profiling Algorithm (ASPA) may offer some advantages for this procedure and will be exemplified below. The ASPA is currently under development in the EU Riskhunt3R project, and this is accompanied by the graphical user interface NAMASTOX (<https://www.risk-hunt3r.eu/aspa/>), which is scheduled for public presentation and release in 2025. More detailed background information may be found using following links: (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8z63MGg71HM>; <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fqk17Y3wz9o>; https://www.risk-hunt3r.eu/wp-content/uploads/RH3R_newsletter_Issue4_FV.pdf. or in Celardo et al., 2025).

Fig. 1: Overview of the processes required to move from screening in NAM to risk assessment

Construction principles of an algorithmic IATA, named ASPA

During the past 15 years, many teams and organisations suggested key elements that need to be considered for an integrated risk assessment (e.g. Leist et al., 2014). The OECD IATA case studies program provides a lot of examples. The ASPA uses the same canonical building blocks as suggested in many other publications (Fig. 2). The problem formulation is considered to be the entry point and it feeds in e.g. the definition of the test chemical and the regulatory questions to be answered. The problem formulation is important for exact definitions of more downstream decision points in the IATA/ASPA procedure. In a next step, already available information would be collected. If not sufficient for risk assessment, three major modules of data generation are activated. The exposure module defines the external exposure, depending on use scenarios, and then links to the toxicokinetics module (ADME) to determine the internal exposure. Important for this is the setup and parametrization of suitable PBK models. A further function of the ADME module would be to provide information on potentially toxic metabolites and specific distribution phenomena (e.g. via specialised transporters). The hazard module would e.g. contain the DNT-IVB for screening. Ideally, relevant mode of action (MoA) and AOPs would be identified (Tal et al., 2024; Leist et al., 2017). PoD would be used for IVIVE for prediction of adverse doses. This information (and the linked uncertainties) would then need to be integrated and interpreted to allow risk assessment.

Building blocks of ASPA

Fig. 2: Overview of the main building blocks of ASPA and of a simplified workflow.

The conventional IATA procedure contains all essential elements and is very flexible. However, the steps taken, the sequence of the steps, the methods used, the decision points and resultant decisions, and the way how information is integrated and used for risk assessment are not defined. Thus, it is likely that groups of experts may arrive at different conclusions, even when faced with similar problem formulations and similar sets of data. ASPA attempts a solution to this problem by suggesting an algorithmic procedure for data generation and interpretation, but also by providing a rationale for the setup of this structure and the selection of methods (Fig. 3). Accompanying the ASPA, a software dashboard is being developed that leads through this procedure, and tracks/documents each step. The vision is that such data are stored for many compounds so that a historical reference base is generated that helps making expert decisions more consistent (Fig. 3).

Moving from a general IATA to ASPA

What is needed:

- Transparent input requirements
- Reliable selection of tools
- Defined data generation
- Solid decision rules
- Reliable data integration procedures
- Confidence in predictivity, reproducibility and relevance
- Documentation, tracking, transparency of each step and each decision
- Reproducibility of outcomes (at given input) and quantification of remaining uncertainties

Fig. 3: Elements important to move from a generic IATA concept to ASPA.

Exemplification of ASPA by a picoxystrobin case study

An exemplification shows best how the ASPA may work, and whether it is applicable to DNT. In a recent screen, initiated by the US NIEHS, picoxystrobin emerged as a hit in some assays. Details may be found in a video recording (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fqk17Y3wz9o>) or an accompanying publication (Magel et al., 2024).

Briefly, picoxystrobin inhibited the migration of neural crest cells in the UKN2 assay. This test (Nyffeler et al., 2017 a;b) is part of the DNT-IVB, and hit confirmation, combined with mechanistic investigations,

showed that the compound blocks mitochondrial function and may reduce cellular energy levels. A PBK model was established (including also foetal compartments), and PoD from NAM testing were converted by IVIVE to expected adverse doses. As an additional correction factor, the uneven distribution of the test compound in cell culture compartments was considered and calculated as explained earlier (Magel et al., 2024, Fisher et al., 2019). To prepare data for risk assessment, it was considered important to give a visual overview of concentration ranges that follow good reporting standards (Hartung et al., 2019) and to allow various comparisons. For instance, based on a maximal exposure, the picoxystrobin concentrations that may be reached in various maternal or foetal compartments were calculated and displayed (Fig. 4). In the same overview, the PoD concentrations obtained from various NAM are displayed. For the most relevant couple of exposure and NAM PoD, also the biokinetics correction factor was displayed and applied. In this context, the term biokinetics refers specifically to distribution phenomena of the test compound in the culture dish. It describes and quantifies differences between the nominal test concentration and predictions of actual concentrations at the intracellular target site. The VIVD model (Fisher et al., 2019) which takes into account compound logP and ionisation of the test compound, cell and medium volumes, as well as protein and lipid content of cell culture compartments, was used. Based on this modelling approach, the highest reached concentration was at least 80 times lower than the concentration required for a biological (or possibly toxic) effect (Fig. 4). When the predicted intracellular concentration that triggered toxicity was used as PoD for in vitro-to-in vivo extrapolation, a threshold human toxic dose of > 7.2 mg/kg/day was predicted.

Development of transparent overview displays for relevant concentration ranges:

- Derive Bioactivity exposure relation (BER) or
- Margin-of-Exposure (MoE)

Fig. 4: Overview of data from the picoxystrobin case study and exemplification of a comparative data overview

Perspectives

It has been addressed here, how the DNT-IVB may be used for risk assessment. The DNT-IVB generates patterns of activity calls: these need to be followed up and then further assessed in an IATA process. It was suggested here to work towards a structured, algorithmically defined IATA, as exemplified by ASPA. The outcome of such an ASPA process was exemplified for picoxystrobin.

Not addressed here was how such outcomes of data integration would be used in risk assessment e.g. for setting of health-based guidance values or for classification and labelling. A final ASPA module would need to provide guidance on this. A stakeholder meeting held at the premises of the BfR in Berlin on 26-28 May 2025 discussed and defined these steps.

The picoxystrobin case study also indicated some scientific problems that need clarification in the future. For instance, the assays of the DNT-IVB are performed in a highly standardised format. This has

advantages for definition of readiness criteria, for comparability of the data and for ease of interpretation. However, the human variability (concerning genetics, metabolic states and exposure times/windows) may be larger (Suciu et al., 2023; Delp et al., 2018) than what is captured by the DNT-IVB NAM. This was exemplified here, by different PoD obtained in medium with glucose (Glu) or with galactose (Gal) (100-fold difference, i.e. going from 0.1 μM to 10 μM),, just to name a simple assay variation (Magel et al., 2024). Future studies need to explore whether and how such additional information can and should be obtained and whether it has an effect on risk assessment.

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